

O'QUVCHILAR BILAN O'QIB TUSHUNISH YA'NI "READING" KO'NIKMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA O.HENRYNING "THE LAST LEAF" HIKOYASI ASOSIDA YANGI METODIK USULLARNI QO'LLASH

¹Muhtaramxon Saidxoshimxon qizi Sayidazimova

Fargona davlat universiteti, Lingvistika(ingliz tili) yo'nalishi,
2-kurs magistranti, Qo'shtepa tuman 16-umumiy o'rta
ta'lim maktabi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi,

²Abbasova Nargiza Kabilovna

Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Chet tili fakulteti katta o'qituvchisi.

muhtaramxonsayidazimova@mail.com.

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarga muammoli mavzulardan biri bo'lgan "Reading, o'qib tushunish mahoratini oshirish" da ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar va interfaol usullardan foydalanildi. Interfaol usullarni amaliy mashg'ulotlarda qo'llash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Maqolada berilgan "Board game", "Matching", "Map of the story", "INSERT", "CINQUAIN" metodlari dars jarayonida qo'llash uchun juda foydali. Ushbu metodlar o'quvchini erkin fikrlashga, mavzuni oson o'zlashtirishga, o'z fikrini dadil ifoda etishga, guruhlar bilan ishlashda, chaqqonlikka undaydi. Shuningdek, maqolada o'qib tushunish, yozish va gapirish ko'nikmalari hamda kichik guruhlarda ishlash uchun mashqlar berilgan

KIRISH

Yosh avlodni chet tillarida o'qitish hamda shu tillarda erkin so'zlasha oladigan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni takomillashtirish negizida, yoshlarning jahon sivilizatsiyasi yutuqlari, shuningdek, butun dunyo axborot resurslaridan foydalanishlari, xalqaro hamkorlik va muloqotni rivojlantirish uchun shart - sharoitlar yaratish asosiy maqsad qilib qo'yiladi. Shu sababdan ham chet tillarini o'rganish bugungi kunning asosiy talabi bo'lib qoldi. Chet tilida o'qib tushunish, eshitish, yozish, gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish - bu chet tili darslarining asosiy maqsadi sanalanadi. Ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning nafaqat keng bilim va

professional malakalarni egallashi, zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot - kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalangan holda o'qitishning ilg'or uslublarni joriy etish yo'li bilan o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodga chet tillarni o'qitish, shu tillarda erkin muloqot qila oladigan mutaxassislarni tayyorlash hamda buning negizida, ularning jahon sivilizatsiyasi yutuqlaridan keng ko'lamda foydalanishlari, ulkan intellektual boylikni egallashlariga katta imkoniyatlar yaratilmoqda.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Biz tavsiya qilmoqchi bo'lgan mavzuning asosiy maqsadi yuqori sinflarni

chet tili darslarida ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar va interfaol usullardan foydalanish hisoblanadi. Chet tillarini o'rgatishdagi o'quvchilarning o'qib tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarning tadbiiq etilishiga oid ilmiy - metodik tavsiyalar bilan boyitildi.

INTERFAOL USULI NIMA?

Dastlab interfaol usul nima ekanligi haqida tushuncha berib o'tsak. Interfaol inglizcha so'z bo'lib, «interact»: «inter» - o'zaro va «act» - harakat qilmoq), ularni umumlashtirganda esa, «Interfaol» - o'zaro harakat qilmoq ma'nosini anglatadi. «Interaction» - hamkorlikni (boshqalar bilan) bildiradi. Ya'ni, o'qitishning interfaol uslublari - bilish va kommunikativ faoliyatni tashkil etishning maxsus shakli bo'lib, unda ta'lim oluvchilar bilish jarayoniga jalb qilingan bo'ladilar, ular biladigan va o'ylayotgan narsalarni tushunish va fikrlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar.

Interfaol usul - bu o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar o'rtasida o'zaro hamkorlik tufayli dars samaradorligini oshirish, yangi darsni o'quvchining mustaqil harakati,

mulohaza, bahs - munozaralar orqali o'rganish, qo'yilgan maqsadga o'zi mustaqil erishish, mikrogruhlarda javob topishga harakat qilishidir, ya'ni o'quvchi fikrlaydi, yozadi, gapiradi, tinglaydi, eng asosiysi o'zi faol ishtirok etadi. Interfaol o'qitish usullari ayniqsa, amaliy mashg'ulotlarda yaxshi samara beradi.

ASOSIY QISM

Quyida biz berilgan mavzuga oid bir nechta interfaol usullarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

Bugungi dars mashg'uloti mavzusi "Reading. "The last leaf" by O.Henry".

1. **Daily routine. Kundalik qoidalar.** O'quvchilarning gapirish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish va o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirish uchun har bir darsda kundalik qoidalarni turli usullarda so'rab borish. Misol uchun, o'qituvchi birinchi savolni beradi, "Who is on duty today?" va qo'lidagi to'pni navbatchi o'quvchiga beradi. Navbatchi o'quvchi hisobotini topshirib bo'lgach boshqa o'quvchiga to'pni savol berib otadi. "What season is it now?", "What is the weather like today?", "What kind of holidays are there in this season?" kabi savollarni bir-birlariga to'pni oshirish orqali beradilar.

2. Uyga berilgan vazifalarni tekshirish “**Board game**” o’yini orqali tekshirib olinadi. Bu usul o’quvchilarni chet tilini o’rganishga bo’lgan qiziqishini oshiradi. Masalan, o’tilgan mavzu tibbiyot sohasiga oid bo’lsa, sinfni 2 guruhga raqamlarni sanash orqali bo’linadi. Guruhlar ikki qator

turib olishadi va qo’llarida tayoqcha bo’ladi. O’qituvchi tibbiyotga oid so’zlarni ingliz tilida izohini aytadi va topgan guruh yugurib borib doskada yopishtirib qo’yilgan so’zlardan to’g’ri javobni uradi. Eng ko’p so’zni topgan guruh g’olib bo’ladi.

Group 1

Group 2

Gurney, stethoscope, ambulance, doctor, nurse, **syringe**, patient, illness, surgeon, laboratory.

3. «INSERT» STRATEGIYASI METODI

Bu usul dastlab Amerikalik olim Voghan Estes tomonidan o’rganilgan. Insert strategiyasi o’quvchilarning matn bilan ishlash ko’nikmasini, avvaldan ma’lum

bo’lgan bilimlarini takrorlashga va yangi bilim bilan boyitishga qaratilgan. Ushbu metodda belgilar bilan ishlanadi. (+, -, v, !, ?)

I	N	S	E	R	T
Interactive	Noting	System for	Effective	Reading and	Thinking

Berilgan matnni o’qishdan oldin o’quvchilar bilimlarini tekshirib oladilar. Agar matndagi ma’lumotlar allaqachon o’quvchilarga ma’lum bo’lsa, “V” belgisiga ma’lumotlarni kiritadilar. Agar matn ular o’ylagan ma’lumotlarga qarama-qarshi berilgan bo’lsa, “-“ belgisiga, va yoki

matndan yangi qiziqarli ma’lumot o’rgangan bo’lsalar “+” belgisi, matndagi biror qiziqqan mavzulari haqida to’liqroq ma’lumot olishni istaganlar “!” belgisini, hamda “?” belgisi o’quvchilar uchun yaxshi tushunmagan noma’lum ma’lumotni kiritish uchun berilgan.

V	-	+	!	?
“The last leaf” was written by O. Henry	I thought that Mr. Pneumonia was a doctor, but It was the name of disease.	Johnsy got well soon with the help of an old artist Mr. Behrman.	Where did Sue work? Did they have parents?	Did they live together? Did the old artist have a family?

The Last Leaf

IN A SMALL PART OF THE CITY WEST OF Washington Square, the streets have gone wild. They turn in different directions. They are broken into small pieces called “places.” One street goes across itself one or two times. A painter once discovered something possible and valuable about this street. Suppose a painter had some painting materials for which he had not paid. Suppose he had no money. Suppose a man came to get the money. The man might walk down that street and suddenly meet himself coming back, without having received a cent! This part of the city is called Greenwich Village. And to old Greenwich Village the painters soon came. Here they found rooms they like, with good light and at a low cost. Sue and Johnsy lived at the top of a building with three floors. One of these young women came from Maine, the other from California. They had met at a restaurant on Eighth Street. There they discovered that they liked the same kind of art, the same kind of food, and the same kind of clothes. So they decided to live and work together. That was in the spring. Toward winter a cold stranger entered Greenwich Village. No one could see him. He walked around touching one person here and another there with his icy fingers. He was a bad sickness. Doctors called him Pneumonia. On the east side of the city he hurried, touching many people; but in the narrow streets of Greenwich Village he did not

move so quickly. Mr. Pneumonia was not a nice old gentleman. A nice old gentleman would not hurt a weak little woman from California. But Mr. Pneumonia touched Johnsy with his cold fingers. She lay on her bed almost without moving, and she looked through the window at the wall of the house next to hers. One morning the busy doctor spoke to Sue alone in the hall, where Johnsy could not hear. “She has a very small chance,” he said. “She has a chance, if she wants to live. If people don’t want to live, I can’t do much for them. Your little lady has decided that she is not going to get well. Is there something that is troubling her?” “She always wanted to go to Italy and paint a picture of the Bay of Naples,” said Sue. “Paint! Not paint. Is there anything worth being troubled about? A man?” “A man?” said Sue. “Is a man worth—No, doctor. There is not a man.” “It is weakness,” said the doctor. “I will do all I know how to do. But when a sick person begins to feel that he’s going to die, half my work is useless. Talk to her about new winter clothes. If she were interested in the future, her chances would be better.” After the doctor had gone, Sue went into the workroom to cry. Then she walked into Johnsy’s room. She carried some of her painting materials, and she was singing. Johnsy lay there, very thin and very quiet. Her face was turned toward the window. Sue stopped singing, thinking that Johnsy was asleep. Sue began to work. As she worked she heard a low sound, again and

again. She went quickly to the bedside. Johnsy's eyes were open wide. She was looking out the window and counting—counting back. "Twelve," she said; and a little later, "Eleven"; and then, "Ten," and, "Nine"; and then, "Eight," and, "Seven," almost together. Sue looked out the window. What was there to count? There was only the side wall of the next house, a short distance away. The wall had no window. An old, old tree grew against the wall. The cold breath of winter had already touched it. Almost all its leaves had fallen from its dark branches. "What is it, dear?" asked Sue. "Six," said Johnsy, in a voice still lower. "They're falling faster now. Three days ago there were almost a hundred. It hurt my head to count them. But now it's easy. There goes another one. There are only five now." "Five what, dear? Tell your Sue." "Leaves. On the tree. When the last

one falls, I must go, too. I've known that for three days. Didn't the doctor tell you?" "Oh, I never heard of such a thing," said Sue. "It doesn't have any sense in it. What does an old tree have to do with you? Or with your getting well? And you used to love that tree so much. Don't be a little fool. The doctor told me your chances for getting well. He told me this morning. He said you had very good chances! Try to eat a little now. And then I'll go back to work.

4. "TARJIMASINI MOSLA" (MATCHING)Texnikasi

Matndagi qahramonlarga berilgan ta'rifga qarab ismlarni moslaydilar. Hikoyadagi nomlarni kartochkalarga bo'lib yoziladi va berkitilgan holatda o'quvchilarga tarqatiladi. Qaysi o'quvchiga bir xil qahramon nomi tushsa, o'sha bitta guruh sanaladi. Bunda o'quvchilarga ma'lum vaqt berilishi kerak bo'ladi.

- Sue – a) a symbol of life
Johnsy – b) toward winter a cold stranger entered Greenwich Village. He was a bad sickness.
Mr. Behrman - c) a young artist, came from California, became seriously ill with Pneumonia
Mr. Pneumonia - d) was a painter who lived on the first floor of their house. He was past sixty. He had had no success as a painter.
A tree - e) a young painter who came from Maine

5. Hikoya xaritasi. (Map of the story).

Berilgan hikoyani tahlil qilishga va yanayam ko'proq tushunishga yordam beradi. Guruhlar bilan ishlashda har bir guruhga hikoyaning bittadan bo'limini tahlil uchun ajratib beriladi.

1	Set (The brief meaning of the story)	The story is about two young girls who tried to live in the hard days because of the disease
2	Main characters	Sue, Johnsy, Mr.Behrman, A doctor
3	Problems	Feeling upset, Not trying to live, etc.
4	Chapter 1	About introduction of the main characters and problem of the story
5	Solution	Calling doctor and trying to find the solution of the problem
6	Theme of the story	Young girl felt miserable and her friend tried to encourage her to live again.
7	What does the story teach?	To live happily, never give up, keep trying, etc.

6. "CINQUAIN" metodi

Ushbu metod fransuz tilidan tarjima qilinganda "cenqueme" "besh, beshinchi" degan ma'nolarni anglatadi. Metod bilan o'quvchining eng muhim ko'nikmasini,

ya'ni xulosa qilish va birgina so'z bilan butun bir hikoyani tahlil qilishga undaydi. **XX** asrning boshlarida Amerikalik shoira Adealida Krepsey "Cinquain" usulini rivojiga hissa qo'shgan.

1 line	Hero of the story. Who? What?	(1 noun) Sue
2 line	Description of the hero?	(2 adjectives) kind, friendly
3 line	Actions of the hero. What does she do?	(3 verbs) helps, encourages, draws
4 line	The phrase about the hero	(4 words phrase) She helps her friend
5 line	Summary describing the essence of the subject	(1 noun) friend

Yuqoridagi namunada ko'rsatilgandek qolgan qahramonlarni boshqa guruhlar ham jadval asosida to'ldirishadi va doskani oldida tahlil qilib beradilar. Shu tariqa hikoyaning barcha qahramonlari haqida to'liq tushuncha hosil bo'ladi va matnni qisqa vaqt ichida o'rganib chiqiladi.

XULOSA

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisining IX sessiyasi (1997 yil 29 avgust) da qabul qilingan O'zbekiston Respublikasining

"Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonunni va "Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturi" mazmunida barkamol shaxs va malakali mutaxassisni tarbiyalab voyaga yetkazish jarayonining mohiyati to'laqonli ochib berilgan. Yuqoridagi maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va interfaol usullardan foydalanish to'g'risida qisqacha ma'lumot berishga va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni ta'limga tadbiiq etishning afzalliklari, yuqori sinflarda xorijiy tillarni

o'qitishda yangi pedagogik qo'llanilishi haqida yoritilishga harakat texnologiyalarning va interfaol usullarning qildik. turlari, ta'lim jarayonida ularning

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